

Effects of Management Style and Work-Life Balance of Employees in Mining Companies in the Katangese Copper Arc

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Abstract: This study aims to analyze the impact of management styles on the work-life balance (WLB) of employees in the mining companies of the Katanga Copperbelt. Given the specific challenges faced by these companies, where reconciling professional and family demands is particularly crucial, the research thoroughly examines the effects of authoritarian, participative, delegative, transformational, transactional, paternalistic, servant, and adaptive management styles on WLB. Through a mixed-methods approach combining qualitative and quantitative analyses (using SPSS and AMOS), the goal is to validate or refute the hypotheses regarding the relationship between these management styles and WLB.

Qualitative results from Iramuteq reveal nuanced employee perceptions of management styles. Certain styles, such as participative and delegative management, are perceived as conducive to balancing work and family life, while authoritarian management is largely viewed as detrimental. However, the quantitative findings indicate that the impact of these styles on WLB is not always statistically significant. For instance, while participative management shows a slight positive influence, the relationship remains non-significant. Similarly, transactional and paternalistic styles demonstrate a slightly negative relationship with WLB, but without statistical significance.

This research highlights the need to adopt management styles that are more attuned to employees' socio-cultural realities, particularly in mining contexts where family plays a central role. However, the results also underscore the limitations of purely quantitative approaches in capturing the full complexity of managerial dynamics.

Keywords: *Work-Life Balance, Management Styles, Mining Companies, Qualitative Analysis, Quantitative Analysis, Katanga Copperbelt, SPSS, AMOS, Iramuteq.*

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I. INTRODUCTION

The Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) is a rich nation in natural resources, particularly minerals such as copper and cobalt. The Katangese Copper Arc, located in the southeast of the DRC, is one of the most important mining regions in the world. This area is crucial to the Congolese economy, representing a substantial part of the country's gross domestic product (GDP) and exports. Mining companies play a vital role here, providing employment to thousands of people and contributing significantly to state tax revenues (World Bank, 2018).

Mineral extraction in the Katangese Copper Arc also has a global impact. Copper and cobalt are essential for various industries, including electronics, green technologies and batteries for electric vehicles. The growing global demand for these minerals accentuates the strategic importance of this region. Working conditions in the mines

of the Katangese Copper Arc are often difficult and dangerous. Workers face health and safety risks, long and irregular working hours, and constant pressure to meet production targets. These conditions can negatively affect employees' work-life balance (WB-WB), leading to stress, burnout and family conflict (ILO, 2017).

Indeed, the challenges linked to WLB have important social implications. Imbalances can lead to mental and physical health problems for workers, affect their productivity and increase turnover. They can also have consequences for family cohesion and social stability, impacting the local communities where employees live.

Management styles in mining companies in the Katangese Copper Arc vary considerably. Some companies adopt management approaches focused on production and results, often to the detriment of employee well-being. Others, on the other hand, attempt to implement more

balanced management practices, integrating family support and work flexibility policies. Managers in this region must navigate a complex environment, where the demands of productivity and profitability must be balanced with the well-being needs of employees (Méda, 2005). Ineffective management practices can increase work-life tensions, while more balanced approaches can improve employee satisfaction and productivity (ILO, 2017).

The regulatory framework in the DRC regarding working conditions and family support policies is under development. Existing regulations may be insufficient or poorly enforced, making it difficult for companies to improve their employees' WLB. A thorough understanding of the specific needs and challenges in this region can inform the development of more effective policies. The Congolese government has shown growing interest in improving working conditions and promoting worker well-being. Initiatives to strengthen regulations and encourage responsible management practices are underway, although much remains to be done to ensure their effective implementation (World Bank, 2018).

Cultural values and norms in the DRC play a crucial role in the perception and management of WLB (Mangala, 2024). Social expectations regarding gender roles, family responsibilities and work practices influence employee experiences. Companies must consider these cultural factors to develop effective management policies and practices. Local culture can also influence employees' expectations of their employers and their management preferences. Understanding these cultural dynamics is essential for managers seeking to promote a balanced work environment and effectively support their employees.

Mining in the Katangese Copper Arc also presents significant environmental challenges, including land degradation, water pollution and impacts on biodiversity. These environmental problems can indirectly affect employees' WLB by creating harsh living conditions for their families and communities. Mining companies are increasingly required to meet environmental responsibility standards, which can influence their management practices and commitment to employee well-being. Integrating sustainable management practices can improve the reputation of companies and contribute to a healthier and more balanced work environment.

Indeed, the interaction between management style and employees' work-family life balance (WLB) constitutes a crucial theme in modern companies, particularly in demanding sectors such as mining. In the context of mining companies in the Katangese Copper Arc, this interaction takes on particular importance due to the rigorous and often dangerous working conditions that characterize this industry.

Current literature shows growing interest in the link between management style and WLB. However, there are still significant gaps, particularly in the African context and more specifically in the Democratic Republic of Congo

(DRC). Authors such as (Allen & Meyer, 1990) explored organizational commitment, while (Greenhaus & Beutell, 1985) examined work-family conflict. However, few studies have addressed these dynamics in the specific context of mining companies in sub-Saharan Africa. The present study aims to fill this gap by providing empirical data and contextual analyses.

This study is crucial for several reasons. First, it provides an in-depth understanding of the impacts of management styles on employees' work-life balance, an essential aspect for worker well-being and productivity. Second, it provides valuable information for managers and policy makers on best practices to improve WLB, thereby contributing to more effective human resource management in the mining sector.

The central problem of this study is to understand how management styles in mining companies influence the work-life balance of employees. This problem is all the more relevant in a sector where working conditions can exacerbate conflicts between professional and personal life.

From our field investigations in mining companies in the Katangese Copper Arc; data relating to working hours and shifts vary between one, two or three going from 7 a.m. to 7 p.m., from 7 p.m. to 7 a.m.; either from 6:30 a.m. to 2:30 p.m., from 2:30 p.m. to 7:30 p.m. and from 7:30 p.m. to 6:30 a.m. or from 7:00 a.m. to 4:00 p.m. outside the journey.

Also, according to the statistics collected, 20% of agents stay on the work site where housing is built (camps) for around $\frac{3}{4}$ of their time compared to $\frac{1}{4}$ of their time with family.

This system of multiple teams per shift allows 24-hour continuity of operations, but can pose challenges in managing fatigue and work-life balance, especially for sites requiring significant travel.

Indeed, the management of working hours, the balance between family and professional life, and management style are closely linked and mutually influence the performance and well-being of employees (Peretti, 2016). A flexible and caring management style, which values work-life balance, can improve employee satisfaction and motivation. For example, flexible work schedules or flexible work hour management policies allow employees to better manage their family responsibilities without compromising their productivity. On the other hand, rigid management focused solely on results can lead to stress and an imbalance between professional and personal life, negatively affecting the performance and morale of employees (Lefrançois, Saint-Charles, Fortin, & des Rivières-Pigeon, 2017). Thus, a management style that promotes balanced management of working hours and supports the balance between family and professional life is essential to create a healthy and productive work environment (Lefèvre, Pailhé, & Solaz, 2008).

Hence our research question: What are the effects of management styles that impact the work-life balance of employees in mining companies in the Katangese Copper Arc?

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The connection between management style and work-life balance has become a central subject in HRM research (Chrétien & Létourneau, 2010) (Ollier-Malaterre, Jacobs, & Rothbard, 2019). Faced with the transformation of working methods, with the rise of flexibility, and increasing demands in terms of productivity, the way in which companies manage these two spheres is crucial for the well-being of employees and organizational performance (Fusilier, Giraldo, & Laloy, 2013). Management style, whether authoritarian, participative or transformational, plays a determining role in the balance that employees can achieve between their professional and personal obligations. Theories such as the theory of leadership styles, the model of (Greenhaus & Beutell, 1985) on work-life balance, or the Job Demands-Resources Model offer relevant conceptual frameworks for understanding how managerial practices influence the ability of employees to reconcile these two dimensions of their lives. This literature review explores these different theoretical frameworks and examines their application in contemporary organizational management.

At the international level, several studies have examined the relationships between management and WLB. For example, (Thomas & Ganster, 1995) demonstrated that perceived organizational support is a crucial factor for WLB. These authors examined the direct and indirect effects of organizational policies and practices that support family responsibilities on work-family conflict and psychological, physical, and behavioral measures of strain (Tanquerel & Grau-Grau, 2020). The results of this research show that supportive practices, particularly flexible schedules and supportive supervisors, had direct positive effects on employees' perceptions of control over work and family matters. Perceptions of control, in turn, were associated with lower levels of work-family conflict, job dissatisfaction, depression, somatic complaints, and blood cholesterol. These findings suggest that organizations can take steps that can increase employees' control over their family responsibilities and that this control could help employees better manage the conflicting demands of work and family life.

Similarly, (Hammer, Kossek, Anger, Bodner, & Zimmerman, 2011) showed that flexible work policies can improve WLB. Indeed, relying on a conceptual model integrating research on training, work-family interventions and social support, they conducted a quasi-experimental field study to evaluate the impact of training for supervisors and a self-monitoring intervention designed to increase supervisors' use of family supports. The results demonstrated a disordered interaction for the effect of training and family-work conflict on employee job satisfaction, turnover intentions, and physical health. Specifically, for these outcomes, positive training effects

were observed for employees with high family-work conflict, while negative training effects were observed for employees with low work-family conflict. family and work. These moderation effects were mediated by the interactive effect of training and family-work conflict on employees' perceptions of supervisors' family-friendly behaviors.

In Africa, research on this theme is limited, but growing. Studies such as those of (Masvaure & M., 2014) in Zimbabwe show that favorable managerial practices have a significant impact on employees' work-life balance.

Research by (Boukheloua, Benabou, & Debbat, 2017) shows that with the interference of work in family life and vice versa the interference of family in the professional sphere, the rise of women in the market of work, the rise of dual-career couples, organizations are increasingly called upon to promote a better balance between the professional and personal lives of their employees. This balance which has become a priority, if not the priority. This research shows how aspects relating to work, notably organizational support, the organization of working hours and the granting of leave, can influence the balance between professional and personal life among women.

In the DRC, the work of (Tchouassi, ga Kamga, & Tomo, 2022) has highlighted the difficult working conditions in mines and the impact on workers' families. However, the specific links between management styles and WLB remain understudied.

However, the unique challenges facing mining companies in the ACK require more localized investigation. So in this research, we will analyze the relationships between management styles and work-life balance of agents in the mining companies of the Katangese copper arc where the phenomenon of work-life balance is acute.

On a theoretical level, the theory of leadership styles (Noguera & Plane, 2016) explains that management style has a direct influence on the way employees manage their balance between professional and family life. Authoritarian leadership, for example, is characterized by tight control and high expectations, with little flexibility in time management. This can create conflict for employees with family responsibilities because they have less flexibility to adjust their schedules. In contrast, more flexible leadership styles, such as transformational or caring leadership, promote employee autonomy, encourage more flexible scheduling and respond to individual needs, thereby facilitating better work-life balance.

The work-life balance theory of (Greenhaus & Beutell, 1985) highlights the conflict that can arise when work and family demands are incompatible. According to this theory, management style directly influences this conflict: rigid management with expectations of constant availability increases the risk of conflict, while flexible and understanding management reduces this tension. If management promotes practices such as flexible hours, parental leave or teleworking, this helps reduce work-family

conflicts, because employees have more control over their schedule. Proactively managing this conflict is crucial to ensuring a healthy balance.

Vroom's expectancy theory explains that employees' motivation to balance work and life depends on their expectations regarding the results of their efforts. If employees perceive that their company values this balance, by offering resources such as flexible hours or accommodations for family obligations, they will be more motivated to achieve this balance. A management style that actively supports these practices sends a clear message that work-life balance is an important goal, thereby increasing employee engagement and satisfaction. Expectations of rewards and recognition therefore play a key role in how employees perceive and manage this balance.

Finally, the Job Demands-Resources Model posits that excessive job demands, such as long hours or high workloads, lead to stress and burnout, especially in the absence sufficient resources (Brulhart, Guieu, & Maltese, 2010). A management style that emphasizes supporting employees by providing them with resources such as flexible working conditions, family support or more flexible time management can reduce pressure and promote better work-life balance. family life. This model shows that the management style must balance job demands with the resources provided to avoid burnout and allow employees to maintain a satisfactory balance between their personal and professional responsibilities.

III. METHODOLOGY

The study used qualitative and quantitative data to provide a comprehensive analysis. Data was collected through surveys, semi-structured interviews and documentary analyses.

The quantitative sample is composed of 384 employees at the 95% confidence threshold and 5% margin of error from different mining companies in the Katangese Copper Arc. 369 responded positively to the questionnaire, which represents a response rate of 96%, this sample was stratified in the different mining sites in the KCA. This sample was composed as follows: 74% men versus 26% women. In relation to age: 30% of the sample between 26 to 35 years old, (22%) between 36 and 45 years old, 21% between 46 and 55 years old, 21% between and 18-25 years old, and 6% between 56-65 years old.

The majority of respondents, i.e. 48%, have achieved a BAC+3 level of education, followed by 28% having a D6 level (end of secondary school diploma). Around 23% of participants hold a BAC+5, while those with studies higher than BAC+6 or D3 are poorly represented, with respectively 1% each.

In relation to marital status, 81% are married, while 19% are single.

We observe that the majority of participants, i.e. 52%, have a seniority of more than 6 years, while 25% have between 0 and 3 years, and 23% have between 4 and 6 years of seniority.

The results indicate that the majority of employees are classified in the mastery category with 51% of participants. Next, 19% of respondents are highly skilled workers, while 17% are management executives and 13% are employees.

The necessary sample for the qualitative approach was composed of 22 agents with saturation threshold criterion.

➤ *Collection Methods And Tools*

- Surveys: A structured questionnaire will be used to collect quantitative data on the perceived management style and WLB of employees.
- Semi-structured interviews: In-depth interviews were conducted with managers and employees to obtain qualitative insights.
- Documentary analyses: Annual reports, company policies and other relevant documents were analyzed to contextualize the empirical data.

➤ *Data Analysis Methods*

- Thematic analysis: Qualitative data from the interviews was analyzed using a thematic approach to identify main themes and trends using Iramuteq software.
- Statistical analysis: Survey data were analyzed using SPSS statistical software to identify significant correlations and impacts.

IV. RESULTS

A. *Qualitative Results*

Based on information obtained through analyzes of lexical classification, factorial correspondence analysis and similarity analysis; the qualitative results are as follows:

- Hypothesis 1 (authoritarian effect): authoritarian style has a negative impact on WLB;
- Hypotheses 2 and 3 (participative and delegative effects): The participatory and delegative styles are perceived positively, linked to better balance;
- Hypotheses 4 and 5 (transformational and transactional effects): These styles are also perceived as having a positive impact on work-family balance;
- Hypothesis 6 (paternalistic effect): The paternalistic style is strongly associated with positive balance;
- Hypothesis 7 (servant effect): The impact of the servant style is perceived positively;
- Hypothesis 8 (adaptive effect): the adaptive style is perceived as favorable to balance.

B. *Statistical Results*

SPSS and AMOS software made it possible to explore the relationship between management styles and work-family life balance (WLB) of employees in mining companies in the Katangese Copper Arc.

The following diagram ultimately emerges which summarizes the overall effect of management styles on work-life balance.

Fig 1 Ultimately Emerges Which Summarizes the Overall Effect of Management Styles on Work-Life Balance.
 Source: Developed from data analysis with SPSS using the AMOS model

➤ *Relationship between Participative and Transformational Management Style and WLB:*

The regression coefficient (λ) between participatory and transformational management and WLB is 0.178, as shown in the table. This coefficient shows a positive, but not significant, relationship with WLB ($p = 0.167$). This result suggests that although participative and transformational management styles have a slight positive influence on work-life balance, this influence is not strong enough to be significant in this model.

Based on this result, the hypothesis corresponding to the positive effect of participative and transformational management on WLB is refuted, because the observed relationship is not statistically significant at the 5% level ($p > 0.05$).

➤ *Relationship between Transactional and Paternalistic Management Style and WLB:*

The regression coefficient between transactional and paternalistic management and WLB is -0.259, indicating a negative relationship with WLB. This coefficient is also not significant ($p = 0.081$). This suggests that transactional and paternalistic management styles have a slightly negative influence on work-life balance, but that this influence is not strong enough to be considered significant.

Consequently, the hypothesis according to which transactional and paternalistic management would have a positive effect on WLB is also refuted, because the negative relationship observed is not statistically significant.

V. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The discussion of the results aims to analyze the relationships observed between the management styles studied and work-family life balance (WLB) by combining qualitative (Iramuteq) and quantitative analyzes (SPSS and AMOS).

➤ *Analysis of Study Hypotheses*

• *Hypothesis 1: Authoritarian Effect*

Qualitative data shows a negative perception of authoritarian management styles. However, the quantitative results of AMOS do not indicate a statistically significant relationship between authoritarian management style and WLB. This hypothesis was not directly tested in the quantitative models provided, but the qualitative results confirm findings in the literature on the negative effects of authoritarian practices on employee well-being, as shown in studies by (Thomas & Ganster, 1995).

- *Participatory and Transformational Effect*

In the qualitative results, several agents expressed their positive perception of participatory and transformational management styles on the balance between professional and family life. However, the quantitative results from AMOS show that this perception is not corroborated by a statistically significant relationship. The estimated regression coefficient for the participatory and transformational effect is 0.178 with a p-value of 0.167, which means that the observed positive relationship is not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). In other words, although this management style is perceived as slightly beneficial, the quantitative data does not confirm a significant influence on WLB.

Thus, hypothesis 2 is refuted based on the quantitative results, despite the positive perceptions collected qualitatively. These results contrast with those of (Thomas & Ganster, 1995), who showed that participatory practices could improve work-family balance.

- *Transactional and Paternalistic Effect*

The qualitative results indicate that some employees perceive the transactional and paternalistic management style as favorable to work-life balance, particularly with regard to goal setting and the family support that these styles can provide. However, the quantitative results reveal a negative relationship between these management styles and WLB, with a regression coefficient of -0.259 ($p = 0.081$). Although this relationship is negative, it is not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$), suggesting that the negative effects are not strong enough to be confirmed quantitatively.

Consequently, hypothesis 5 is invalidated, because the relationship between transactional and paternalistic management and WLB is non-significant and slightly negative. This differs from the results of (Boukheloua, Benabou, & Debbat, 2017), who showed that paternalistic styles could be favorable to work-family balance in certain cultural contexts.

- *Servant Effect*

The qualitative results suggest that servant management is perceived to have a positive effect on WLB, because it involves emotional and organizational support for employees. However, it appears that the quantitative results did not confirm this effect with sufficient statistical strength. The qualitative data highlights a favorable perception, but the quantitative relationship remains to be confirmed in other studies to draw more robust conclusions.

Combining qualitative and quantitative analyses, we observe significant discrepancies between employee perceptions and measured quantitative relationships. Although certain management styles (participative, transformational, and serving) are perceived positively by employees, the quantitative analyzes were not able to confirm in a statistically significant way an influence of these styles on work-family life balance.

These results suggest several possible explanations. First, it is likely that the specific context of mining companies in Katanga, with rigid and hierarchical working conditions, influences the perception of management styles. The transactional style, for example, although viewed favorably by some employees, did not show a significant positive effect in the quantitative results. It is possible that more rigid management styles are better adapted to the mining environment, which could explain the divergences with the results obtained in other sectors studied in the literature (Hammer, Kossek, Anger, Bodner, & Zimmerman, 2011).

Finally, this discussion highlights the importance of considering organizational culture and sectoral context in interpreting the effects of management styles on work-family balance. Mining companies, with their hierarchical structures and strict production requirements, may require particular adaptations of managerial practices to truly improve WLB.

In summary, this study found that although employees generally perceived participative, transformational, and servant styles as having a positive impact on WLB, the quantitative results failed to confirm these effects in a statistically significant way. This highlights the complexity of the relationships between management styles and work-family balance in the context of mining companies in Katanga and suggests the need for future studies to better understand these dynamics.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study aimed to analyze the effects of management styles on the work-family life balance (WLB) of employees in mining companies in the Katangese Copper Arc. In a context where socio-economic and cultural challenges strongly influence the quality of life at work, it was essential to examine how different management styles: participatory, transformational, authoritarian, transactional, paternalistic, etc., impacted this fragile balance between life, personal and professional. The main objective was to understand how management styles influence the WLB of employees in mining companies in the Katangese Copper Arc.

To achieve this objective, we adopted a mixed methodology, integrating qualitative and quantitative tools. Iramuteq, SPSS and AMOS software were used to analyze the collected data. This methodological approach allowed us to answer the main questions asked by using both semi-structured interviews and structured questionnaires.

The results show that participative and transformational management styles are perceived positively by employees. However, quantitative analyzes did not reveal statistically significant effects on WLB. This contrast raises important questions about the translation of managerial perceptions into concrete results within mining companies. The results partly confirm the work of (Thomas & Ganster, 1995) and (Ernst Kossek & Ozeki, 1998) on the importance of organizational support, but also show that certain

management styles do not always have the expected effect. in the context of Katanga. On a managerial level, the results show that it is crucial for mining companies to adapt their management practices to local cultural realities. Management styles that include organizational support and scheduling flexibility are recommended to improve work-life balance. Despite employees' positive expectations of participatory and transformational styles, these practices must be reinforced by concrete actions for them to produce significant effects on WLB.

However, this research has certain limitations. Theoretically, the study focused on eight specific management styles, without including other dimensions related to well-being or job satisfaction that could have completed the analysis. Empirically, although the qualitative data revealed clear perceptions of employees, the quantitative results did not allow certain hypotheses to be validated due to the specific socio-economic context of Katanga. Methodologically, the mixed approach used showed limitations in the convergence of qualitative and quantitative results, suggesting the need to use more complex statistical methods in future research.

This study opens several research perspectives. Empirically, it would be interesting to expand the sample to other regions or sectors in order to test the validity of the results obtained. Theoretically, the integration of additional variables, such as psychological well-being or job satisfaction, would make it possible to refine the analysis of the relationships between management and WLB. Finally, methodologically, future research could use more advanced statistical methods, such as mixed effects models, to better capture the complexity of interactions between variables.

Ultimately, mining companies in Katanga should adapt their management practices to local realities while strengthening policies supporting WLB. By adopting more inclusive and flexible managerial practices, companies will not only be able to improve the well-being of their employees, but also increase their productivity and engagement, thus contributing to their overall performance.

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